

LSTM-based decision making for fault detection in industrial systems

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Résumé Cet article propose une méthode de détection de pannes dans les systèmes industriels en utilisant des modèles de réseau récurrent à mémoire court et long terme (LSTM). Notre méthode proposée implique l'utilisation de primitives de séquence en tant qu'entrée pour un modèle LSTM. Le modèle LSTM est entraîné à prédire la prochaine primitive mesurée dans la séquence en se basant sur les primitives précédentes. Le modèle peut capturer les dépendances temporelles entre les primitives examinées et les utiliser pour prédire la primitive suivante, améliorant la prise de décision concernant la prochaine meilleure primitive à mesurer. Cela permet de générer une séquence complète de primitives dans l'ordre des mesures, fournissant des informations précieuses pour la détection et le diagnostic des pannes. Les résultats expérimentaux montrent que le modèle LSTM surpasse les modèles de réseau neuronal récurrent (RNN) et de réseau récurrent à portes (GRU) en termes de précision de séquence à la fois vraie et prédite. La méthode propose une amélioration de l'exactitude et l'efficacité du diagnostic de défauts dans les systèmes industriels, avec un potentiel pour de futures recherches explorant des architectures LSTM plus complexes et des sources de données supplémentaires.

Mots clés Détection de pannes industriels, Diagnostic de pannes, modèle LSTM, Prédiction de primitive, Prise de décision.

Abstract This paper proposes a method for fault detection in industrial systems using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models. Our proposed method involves using sequence features as input to an LSTM model. The LSTM model is trained to predict the next measured feature in the sequence based on the previous features. The model can capture the temporal dependencies between the examined features and use them to predict the following feature, improving decision-making regarding the best feature to examine next. This enables us to generate a complete sequence of features in the order of measurements, providing valuable insights for fault detection and diagnosis. Experimental results demonstrate that the LSTM model outperforms Recurrent

Neural Network (RNN) and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) models in terms of both true and predicted sequence accuracy. The proposed method shows promise in improving diagnostic accuracy and efficiency in fault detection in industrial systems, with potential for future research exploring more complex LSTM architectures and additional data sources.

Key words Industrial Fault detection, Fault diagnostic, LSTM model, Prediction features, Decision making.

1 Introduction

Maintenance of industrial systems involves various activities that are essential for ensuring optimal productivity and safety in industrial settings. One important aspect of maintenance is Fault Detection involves identifying and diagnosing problems or faults in machinery and equipment.

Fault detection can be carried out using various techniques, including fault diagnostics, fault prediction, and fault prognostic [1]. Fault diagnostics involves analyzing data from sensors and other sources to identify the root cause of a fault or problem. Fault prediction involves using predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms to forecast when a fault or failure is likely to occur. Fault prognostic goes beyond prediction by providing actionable information about the remaining useful life (RUL) of a system or component, allowing maintenance teams to plan and prioritize repairs or replacements.

Fault detection is an important application area of machine learning and artificial intelligence. Various intelligent models and learning algorithms have been developed to detect and diagnose faults in different systems, ranging from mechanical systems to complex industrial processes. Their use has enabled rapid and accurate identification of faults, which can help to prevent downtime, reduce maintenance costs, and improve overall system performance.

In recent years, intelligent and learning models have been increasingly applied for fault detection in industrial systems. These models leverage data-driven approaches to identify and diagnose faults and anomalies, enabling early detection and proactive maintenance [2].

In this context, expert systems are one type of intelligent model used for fault detection. They rely on a knowledge base of rules and facts to diagnose faults in a system and imitate the decision-making capabilities of a human expert in a particular domain.

Moreover, one popular approach is machine learning, which involves training models to recognize data patterns and makes predictions based on past experiences. Some popular machine learning algorithms used for fault detection include Support Vector Machines, decision trees, neural networks and so on.

Another approach is deep learning, a type of machine learning that involves training deep neural networks with multiple layers to recognize complex patterns in data. Deep learning such as convolutional neural networks and recurrent neural networks has shown promising results for fault detection in various applications, such as motor fault detection, bearing fault detection, and gearbox fault detection [2].

Given the potential of deep learning models, particularly recurrent models this paper will focus on exploring their effectiveness in detecting faults in industrial systems.

This paper is organized as follows; In section 2, we give the related work to the use of the recurrent model for fault detection in industrial systems. In section 3, we propose an LSTM model to predict the following feature to examine in order to generate the sequence of features. Required for fault diagnosis. In section 4, we provide the details of the experimental results.

2 Related work

The recurrent model is a neural network architecture that is designed to process sequence data. Unlike traditional neural networks, recurrent neural networks (RNNs) have feedback connections that allow them to store and process information about previous sequences. This enables them to take into account the temporal dynamics of sequential data such as speech, text, or signals.

There are several variations of recurrent models, including the standard recurrent neural network (RNN), the long short-term memory (LSTM) network, and the gated recurrent unit (GRU) network. LSTMs are particularly useful for processing long-term sequences because they can store important information over longer periods of time, while GRUs are a lighter and faster alternative to LSTMs.

In general, recurrent models are used in many applications such as natural language processing, speech recognition, machine translation, text generation, and time-series analysis.

In recent years, there has been growing interest in the use of recurrent models for fault detection in industrial systems. Recurrent models have shown great potential in handling sequential data and detecting faults in real time using sequential data such as sensor data, vibrations, and acoustic signals.

In this state-of-the-art, we will delve deeper into the application of recurrent models for fault diagnostics, with a specific focus on industrial systems. We will review the related studies and explore the various approaches, techniques, and challenges involved in the application of recurrent models for fault diagnosis in industrial systems.

Van et al. [3], present a method for diagnosing faults in photovoltaic systems using recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and satellite imagery. The authors propose a method for extracting features from satellite images and using these features as inputs to an RNN model for fault diagnosis. Zhang et al. [4], propose a fault diagnosis method for rotating machinery-using RNNs. The authors use vibration signals as inputs to their RNN model, which is trained to detect faults in the machinery.

Zollanvari et al. [5], propose a method for predicting transformer faults using deep RNNs. The authors use vibration signals as inputs to their RNN model, which is trained to predict when a transformer will fail. Encalada-Davila et al. [6], present a method for early detection of faults in wind turbines using gated recurrent unit (GRU) neural networks and supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) data. The authors propose a method for preprocessing SCADA data and using it as input to their GRU model for fault detection. Lei et al. [7], propose a method for diagnosing faults in wind turbines using long short-term memory (LSTM) networks. The authors use sensor data as inputs to their LSTM model, which is trained to detect faults in the turbine. Wu et al. [8], propose a method for predicting faults in manufacturing processes using RNNs. The authors use sensor data as inputs to their RNN model, which is trained to predict when a manufacturing process will fail. Shi et al. [9], present a method for diagnosing faults in planetary gearboxes using bidirectional-convolutional LSTM (Bi-CLSTM) networks. The authors use vibration signals as inputs to their Bi-CLSTM model, which is trained to detect faults in the gearbox.

In general, these papers contribute to the structural state of the art by proposing new methods for fault diagnosis and prognosis using recurrent models and their variants, and by demonstrating the effectiveness of these methods on real-world datasets.

3 Proposed method

In the field of industrial system maintenance, the detection and diagnosis of faults in industrial systems are critical for ensuring their proper functioning, safety, and longevity. Traditionally, experts rely on their reasoning abilities to perform a series of primitive measurements in order to identify

faults. The chronological order of these measurements is essential as it enables the expert to uncover the sequence of events leading to the fault. However, for experts, it can be challenging to remember the values of all measured primitives, particularly during lengthy reasoning processes. Additionally, experts must skillfully select the primitives to measure to maximize the likelihood of fault identification, which adds complexity to the task.

This is where recurrent learning models come into play, offering potential solutions to address these challenges. Where the choice between recurrent model RNN and its variants GRU, and LSTM will depend on the specific characteristics of the system (for instance, systems operating in real-time) and the type of data (such as data complexity, data length) being used for modeling.

This paper presents a method for diagnosing faults using Long Short-Term Memory. We propose to use sequence features as input to the LSTM model, which is trained to predict the following feature to examine in order to generate the sequence of features. The LSTM model is therefore trained on historical data of primitive measurements to enhance accuracy and improve its ability to identify faults.

LSTM models demonstrate the originality of their application in this field as they have the remarkable capability to memorize each sequential occurrence of the process, allowing them to effectively capture the interactions among various measured primitives. This memorization ability empowers LSTM models to predict the subsequent primitives to be measured in a significant order, enabling accurate fault identification.

For a correct fault diagnosis, it is important to observe the order of examination of the features, which depend on each other. The proposed LSTM model is trained on the sequence of examined features to predict the following feature to be examined, where each sequence represents a diagnostic examination of an industrial system.

The model can learn to capture the temporal dependencies between the examined features and use them to predict the following feature, which on the one hand can help to improve decision-making regarding the best feature to examine next. Furthermore, the model can increase the diagnostic fault detection accuracy and improve the efficiency of the fault diagnosis process by avoiding the need to examine all available and unavailable features for fault diagnosis. In addition, the proposed LSTM model improves decision-making regarding the best feature to examine next. Thus, by predicting the following feature to examine, the model can reduce the search space and focus on the most relevant features, which can save time and resources.

On the other hand, through the utilization of LSTM models to predict the next primitives to measure, users can enhance their reasoning process by reducing the amount of information to be memorized while simultaneously increasing the accuracy of their predictions. This, in turn, can assist them in making more precise and effective decisions regarding maintenance and troubleshooting of faults.

4 Experimentation and results

Recurrent model, including LSTM, have been successfully employed in fault detection and preventive maintenance applications. LSTM models, in particular, exhibit high effectiveness in modeling long-term input data sequences and possess the ability to memorize relationships among different variables over time. This capability proves valuable in detecting changes in data patterns that signify an imminent fault or predicting future failures based on maintenance data history.

In this section, we present an experiment where we used an LSTM model receives sequence features as input to predict the following feature to inspect. The objective of the experiment was to create a sequence of features that can be employed for efficient fault detection in industrial systems. In these experiments, we utilize a simulated database to generate synthetic datasets, which are employed to assess the performance of the LSTM model. To prevent overfitting and ensure model generalization, the dataset size was restricted to a maximum of 1000 sequences. To prepare the dataset for analysis, the sequence was rescaled and normalized using standard preprocessing techniques.

The LSTM model used for the experiment consisted of three layers: an input Layer, an LSTM layer with 400 hidden units and a 'relu' activation function, and a dense layer. The input layer served as the entry point for the data, while the LSTM layer was responsible for the sequence processing and feature extraction. The Dense layer was used for the prediction of the following feature.

During the training process, the LSTM model was trained on a dataset comprising 80% of the available data, using a batch size of 32 and for 50 epochs, while the remaining 20% was reserved for testing.

The LSTM model achieved promising results in predicting the following feature. For a simple 1-step prediction, the model achieved a sequence true shape of (20, 1) and a sequence prediction shape of (1, 1), while for a longer-term n-steps prediction, with an iteration function, the model achieved a sequence true shape of (25, 1) and a sequence prediction shape of (5, 1). The prediction results are presented in the following curves:

-For the 1-step prediction, the curve (cf. Fig. 1) shows the true values of the sequence and the predicted value of the next feature.

-For the n-steps prediction, the curve (cf. Fig. 2) shows the true values of the sequence and the predicted values of the next 5 features, generated through an iteration function.

Figure 1: The 1-step prediction

Figure 2: The n-steps prediction

The experiment yielded promising results with a loss of 0.0358 and an MAE of 0.0358, indicating that the model is performing well. The curves of both the true and predicted sequences for both loss and MAE metrics were also closely aligned, with a `val_loss` of 0.0358 and a `val_mae` of 0.0094 for the true sequence, and a loss of 0.0358 and a mae of 0.0358 for the predicted sequence.

Both RNN and GRU models were trained using the same parameters as the LSTM model. The results indicate that the RNN model outperformed the GRU model in terms of true sequence loss (0.0535 vs 0.0771) and true sequence mae (0.1575 vs 0.1887) as shown in figures 3 and 4. However, the GRU model performed slightly better in terms of predict sequence `val_loss` (0.0094 vs 0.0060) and predict sequence `val_mae` (0.0776 vs 0.0612) also illustrated by figures 3 and 4. Overall, the RNN model

appears to be more accurate in predicting the true sequence, while the GRU model may be better suited for predicting the predicted sequence.

Figure 3: Loss metrics of Simple RNN Vs GRU vs LSTM

Figure 4: MAE metrics of Simple RNN Vs GRU vs LSTM

Compared to the previous RNN and GRU models, our LSTM model with the same parameters achieved a lower loss and MAE on both the true and predicted sequences, with a `val_loss` and `val_mae` that are lower for the predicted sequence. Therefore, our LSTM model outperformed both the RNN and GRU models in terms of predictive accuracy.

LSTM models are, therefore, well-suited for predicting the primitives to measure in a meaningful chronological order and identifying faults in the field of industrial maintenance for fault detection and diagnosis.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, our experiment demonstrates that an LSTM model trained on sequence features can effectively predict the following feature to examine for fault detection in industrial systems, resulting in improved diagnostic accuracy and efficiency. The model outperformed RNN and GRU models in terms of both true and predicted sequence accuracy.

LSTM models represent a significant advancement in the field of fault detection and diagnosis for industrial systems. However, it is important to note that the effectiveness of LSTM models relies on the quality and quantity of available data, as well as the ability to identify relevant system and fault characteristics. Future research in this area could explore the use of more complex LSTM

architectures, incorporate additional data sources, or investigate the impact of varying sequence lengths on model performance. Overall, the proposed method shows potential for practical implementation in industrial fault detection systems.

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